

The Performance Analysis For Acceptance Of E-Government Culture In Pakistan Perspectives

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Abstract:

The focus of this paper is to analyze the factors on which a developing country such as Pakistan may adopt the e-Government culture and provide the basis in its adoption with supply and demand perspectives. For this purpose UTAUT model is used as the demand perspectives to incorporate the demand side factors. The obstacles and challenges are also analyzed when adoption of e-Government culture occur. The analyze methods are based on survey with the help of questionnaire in order to collect the qualitative data with a particular sample size. This study focus on citizens with different backgrounds are interviewed. The statistical analysis such as factor analysis, reliability and validity, correlation test, ANOVA and regression analysis which will be supportive in testing the hypotheses related to the supply side and demand side factors in this research.

Keywords: e-Government Adoption, ICT infrastructure, UTAUT model, Culture, Pakistan.

1. Introduction

The ICT (Information and Communication technologies) advancements is expanding the use of the new technologies and making this era more innovative. ICT has enabled the people of this globe to enhance the services and make the use of technology easy (Bohari, 2013). The government of Pakistan is also taking actions in enhancing the use of ICT in every field such as agriculture, textile and etc to bring the culture of e-Government in Pakistan. The projects of e-government and its implementation have become the worldwide phenomenon to provide an effective change in the different fields with the help of innovative and ICT based applications. The goal of the government in e-services is to provide such platform digitally, economically, and morally to become closer to the government on the basis of advancement in ICT (Jaeger, 2009).The Ministry of Information Technology, Pakistan was established in the year 2000 and introduced the e-Government directorate under this ministry.

The use of ICT advancement and its infrastructure is most effective way for the government of Pakistan to adopt the projects related to e-culture which increases the responsibility and transparency within the governmental organizations. The projects on the initial phases include, various connected registrations, civil computerized state databases, and modern universities to provide platform for ICT in all provinces (Bohari, 2013). However, in order to create the automation in the online mapping, land record system and public cartographical data, the government introduced many programs such as government web portals and compulsory computer training programs at all levels of provincial and federal employees (Wicander, 2011). Government spends many dollars in implementing these programs for the betterment of the country. Furthermore, the focus of the paper is on pointing out those factors which are becoming the barriers in adoption of e-government culture in Pakistan. In continuation to the purpose of this paper, the research questions and hypothesis based on the perspective of demand and supply are described below.

1.1 Research Questions

Question 1: Is there a linear relationship between e-Government culture and advancements in ICT in Pakistan?

Question 2: Is there a linear relationship of social values, efforts expectancy and performance expectancy with e-Government culture in Pakistan?

- Question 3: Are the deployment of e-Government applications and policies of government related to each other?
- Question 4: What is the influence of perceived ease of use of websites of e-Government on the culture of e-Government in Pakistan?
- Question 5: What is the support of citizens in bringing e-Government culture to perseverance usefulness of e-Government applications and websites?
- Question 6: Do the proper use of ICT infrastructure impact positively on e-government culture in perseverance ease of use?
- Question 7: Do the level of user's willingness in ICT influence directly the intentions to engage e-Government culture in Pakistan?
- Question 8: Is there a high level of computer self-efficacy which could impact on the actual use of an e-Government system by the citizens of Pakistan?

1.2 Research Hypotheses

H₁: There is linear relationship between e-government culture and advancements in ICT in Pakistan.

H₂: There is a linear relationship of social values, efforts expectancy and performance expectancy with e-government culture in Pakistan.

H₃: The deployment of e-government applications and policies of government are related to each other.

H₄: Perceived ease of use of websites related to e-government will positively influence the culture of e-government in Pakistan.

H₅: Perceived usefulness of websites related to e-government will positively supported by citizen's of Pakistan to bring e-government culture.

H₆: The proper use of ICT infrastructure may impact positively on e-government culture in perseverance ease of use.

H₇: The level of user's willingness in ICT may directly influence the intentions to engage e-government culture in Pakistan.

H₈: There is a high level of computer self-efficacy which could impact on the actual use of an e-government system by the citizens of Pakistan.

1.3 Significance of the Study (Practical and Theoretical Approaches)

E-government is an important public policy topic to research and explore, especially as Internet use increases. Although the literatures reveal that, there have been several studies have done most of developed countries on the demand and supply side perspective separately. In the case of Pakistan, to date, there is a lack of empirical evidence and no such studies completed collectively by examine the both factors jointly which influencing on the adoption of e-Government context. Filling this gap in the literature is one of the motivations for conducting this research with different cultures and values, ICT infrastructure and its applications etc. In addition, as mentioned earlier literature reported the low level of the adoption in e-Government services is particularly noticeable in Pakistan public sector. Therefore, is research is significant because it tries to deliver some contributions for economic, socio-culture and technology development to the field of e-Government adoption. To begin with, this research is going to add to the body of knowledge currently existing within the domain of the adoption of the e-Government. Moreover, this research is aimed at formulating a comprehensive

conceptual framework model that can enlighten effective adoption. Further, it will identify the main challenges and barriers that might influence the adoption expectations for the both side use of e-Government adoption in Pakistan.

2. Literature Review

The perfect implementation of the e-government services is very challenging for every government around the globe and it needs strenuous efforts to make it a reality (Bonsón, 2012). The e-government programs have been commonly used worldwide including Pakistan since 2000 to enhance the service quality and make it faster and reachable to every citizen. Various surveys and studies are now being done in different sectors at governmental level to see the success report from citizen's point of view (Belanger, 2008). It is the responsibility of every citizen to put their best efforts whether they are at work or home to make the e-services worthwhile. The e-government services give the citizens freedom of choice that includes all types of information available online at ease (Elbahnasawy, 2014).

E-Government can be defined as connecting people electronically with the government to be served with the effectiveness of different e-services. It gives the users numerous services that the government is providing electronically under the umbrella of e-services. E-government services initializes with the aim to provide customers value added services at their home or work place i.e. delivering better and faster services, increasing satisfaction on individual level, and building trust on the services provided by the government (Bonsón, 2012).

To broadly understand the demands of the e-government, UTAUT (The Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology) model is used to give the finest overview (Im, 2011). The UTAUT model is built on four main demands that might be used to examine the final response of the citizens using e-services under any Government. These demands are effort expectancy, social influence, facilitating conditions and performance expectancy (Alshehri, 2012). These demands examine the age, gender, experience and voluntariness of use of the country's citizens and then find out the demand scale of the e-services provided by the government.

2.1 Demand Perspectives

The government of Pakistan could incorporate the demand side factors highlighted by UTAUT model as shown in figure 1 in the supply side of e-government services in order to achieve the goals of the e-government culture (Alshehri, 2012). From the perspectives of Demand in bringing the e-government system in Pakistan, most factors are involved which are described below;

- Citizen Support to E-government
- E-government Deployment
- Performance Expectancy
- Effort Expectancy
- Social Influence
- Level of E-government Services
- Financial Resource
- Government Policies
- ICT Infrastructure

Figure 1: Study UTAUT Model

2.2 Supply Perspectives

From the perspectives of Supply in bringing the e-government system in Pakistan, most factors are involved which are described below;

- Perceived Ease of Use of ICT
- Perceived Usefulness of ICT in Pakistan
- Actual usage of E-government Applications
- Computer Self Efficacy
- Continuous usage of E-government Applications
- Users Willingness
- E government Adoption
- E-government Advancement
- Facilitating Condition

2.3 Challenges and Obstacles (Supply and Demand Perspectives)

The factors which become barrier and the challenges which are faced by the government of Pakistan in E-government adoption are issues and problems related to the financial resources, high rates of illiteracy, and low level of the computer knowledge among the population. Some other factors are also creating the issues for the current government of Pakistan such as the policies and strategies of the government in accordance with the management and leadership (Kessides, 2013). The government of Pakistan is facing big challenges in bringing the e-government culture in Pakistan as there is a big lack of skilled people and strength of the human resource in Pakistan. The public sector working in the different organizations, firms and governmental institutions are not providing the satisfactory results and there is also no collaboration found between them.

The environment is filled out with the huge level mismanagement and corruption (Rahman, 2014). Pakistan, in all means is a low income and agricultural country and the large amount of its budget is spent on the defense. In order to construct an ICT infrastructure, the people of this country requires the basic facilities and solution of the problems such as electricity crisis (Kessides, 2013). Being Pakistan an atomic state it is a big question mark on the state being atomic that the issues related to electricity have not yet been resolved (Bhutto, 2013). The government of Pakistan should look into the causes of these issues and provide a solution for these problems in order to adopt the e-government culture.

The government of Pakistan, management of the firms, leaders and scholars, must take the positive actions in improving the policies and strategies in favor of e-government adoption. The priority of government policies and law situation of the country is to fight against terror and war to clear the vision of the people. The phenomenon of instability is found in the current situation and policies of Pakistan (Rehman, 2012). The aim of the successful implementation cannot be achieved until public sector, governmental agencies and department is

filled with the less professional employees. The factor of continuous unsatisfactory performances may take the country at down levels. There are also the different types of hurdles and factors which are faced by the people of Pakistan. The main problems for the common citizen of Pakistan are electricity (Bhutto, 2013). A large number of the urban and rural areas in Pakistan, where the majority of the people live, are facing the problems and issues related to the shortage of electricity. The load shedding must be stopped which could help in constructing the structure of ICT in a better way (Kaul, 2014).

The trust level of the people of Pakistan to the government is also same as the literacy rate of Pakistan i.e. low (Mahmood, 2014). The previous years of the government in Pakistan proved that the services provided by the government such as internet services, online services, unfriendly behavior of web, language barriers, issues for accessibility to the internet, high cost of internet, and malware and security issues have a bad impact on the trust of people of Pakistan (Manzoor, 2013). The people of Pakistan have less participation in the services of governments because of such issues and the citizen’s preferred manual work rather than working in e-government environment. This leads to less generation of online taxes.

Figure 2: Literacy Rates Comparison

Country	Literacy rate
United Kingdom	99%
United States	99%
Canada	99%
Qatar	96%
Australia	96%
Singapore	96%
China	95%
Bahrain	95%
Libya	94%
Kuwait	94%
Tunisia	88%
Saudi Arabia	87%
United Arab Emirates	78%
India	74%
Pakistan	55%
Afghanistan	28%
Bhutan	53%

Source: UNESCO Institute for Statistics.

Figure 3: Literacy Map in Pakistan

Source: <http://nhdr.undp.org/wp-content/uploads/2015/02/Taimur-Rahman-Internet-Youth-Education-in-Pakistan.pdf>

From the above figure 2 and figure 3, it can be noted that the literacy rate of Pakistan as compare to the other countries is very low. The literacy rate for Pakistan is 55% which is only above two countries in literacy rates such as Afghanistan and Bhutan. There is also the need of highlighting the point of awareness regarding e-culture among Pakistanis. Since, Karachi is one of the big cities of the world but there is a lack of technology awareness found among Pakistanis (Bwalya, 2012). The websites are not friendly and also are not in the national language. People do not like to participate in buying or selling online because of low trust level.

2.4 E-government in Developing Countries

A central argument in this study is that the impact of E-government on government-citizen interactions is influenced by a combination of factors, and that the attributes of government websites essential to their usability, their impact on services and information delivery, and their contribution to the transformation of government-citizen relations. It is therefore necessary to examine these web attributes as a means of confirming claims and predictions about social change (Kwak, Skoric, Williams and Poor 2004). Further, this study argues that while the necessary conditions for the effective implementation and utilization of electronic government are not available in developing countries, the status of government websites, as developed so far, have not been subjected to direct and critical empirical observation in spite of the rapid proliferation of the Internet as a medium of communication (Kwak, Skoric, Williams and Poor 2004).

Developed countries are more technologically advanced than less developed countries and have better trained and qualified technologically trained workers (Jensen 2007). The attainment of education, skills and financial resources needed to support IT departments which would implement E-government, remain a challenge for less developed countries. Comparisons of the size and capabilities of infrastructures reveal considerable differences between developed and developing countries (Jensen 2007). Developed nations have the base levels and capacities to make Internet and phone access accessible to just about the majority of their occupants, some with populaces in excess of 300 million. The lacking base of creating nations, due to investment conditions and administrative regulations of information transfers businesses ruin the advancement of E-government in these nations (Jensen 2007).

Differences	Developed	Developing
History & Culture	Government and economy developed early, immediately after independence Economy growing at a constant rate, productivity increasing. High standard of living relatively long history of democracy and more transparent government policy	Government usually not specifically defined Economy not increasing in productivity Low standard of living relatively short history of democracy and less transparent government policy
Technical Staff	Has a current staff, needs to increase technical abilities and hire younger professionals Has outsourcing abilities and financial resources to outsource; Current staff would be able to define requirements for development	Does not have a staff, or has very limited in-house staff Does not have local outsourcing abilities and rarely has the financial ability to outsource; Current staff may be unable to define specific requirement
Infrastructure	Good current infrastructure High Internet access for employees and citizens	Bad current infrastructure Low Internet access for employees and citizens
Citizens	High Internet access and computer literacy; still has digital divide and privacy issues Relatively more experienced in democratic system and more actively participate in governmental policy-making process	Low Internet access and citizens are reluctant to trust online services; few citizens know how to operate computers Relatively less experienced in democratic system and less active participation in governmental policy-making process
Government Officers	Decent computer literacy and dedication of resources; many do not place e-government as a high priority	Low computer literacy and dedication of resources; many do not place e-government at a high priority due to lack of knowledge on the issue

3. Methodology

The methodology which is used in the current study is based on the qualitative analysis.

The aims and the questions for the research are taken into account for the relevant literature in order to specify the appropriate methodology in conducting the research. The importance of the methodology lies in the guidance phenomenon for the researcher as the basic purpose of the methodology is to answer the research questions in order to fulfill the relative objectives (Cohen, 2000). The collected data will be used to analyze the various factors which have the direct or inverse relation with the adoption of e-government system. Various statistical methods to test the hypothesis in this research study are used such as ANOVA and regression analysis (Bonsón, 2012). Prior of conducting the tests, the data is checked for the assumptions of tests such as normality of data and the reliability and validity factor.

The research study employed a methodology with the interpretation that will be utilized in the research in collecting the qualitative data with the help interviewing to ask the related research questions. Such methodology and interpretations of the various types in e-government adoption are required to outline and for the purpose of coding with the numerous possible meanings within the various interpretations (Snead, 2014). Such investigation based on technology may be an interpretive investigation which will be constructed by the discussion and asking the questions. The perspective of such study will be helpful in limiting from the respondents the intended interpretations. The methodology respect to the interpretation in order to apply all these perspectives are required to select in a proper way for all the reasons related to the e-government system problems and its culture for this significant research study.

3.1 Research Participants

The distributions of the participants use in this particular research study is based on the different people including, students, government teachers, scholars, government employees, engineers, employees in the different organizations, low, high and middle class people and etc from the different developed as well as undeveloped cities of Pakistan. The study is designed in such a manner that it comprises of the series of different preliminary tests (Ahmad, 2013). The distributions of the participations are based on the five different groups from which with the help of the interview questions the qualitative data has been extracted. In the preliminary stages, the interviews conducted with government workers such as line ministries to take prior knowledge about the current situation of e-government system in Pakistan. These interviews were helpful to understand the present issues and problems in bringing e-government system and implement at the best possible level in Pakistan. The challenges that are to be faced and the future prospects to implement such system in Pakistan are discussed. The pilot study targeted a sample of 60 respondents from which only 50 respondents took part actively. Thus, response rate was 83% which is a phenomenon of the survey to provide the reliable results. In this regard, total of 17 independent variables and one dependent variable are used. The questionnaire of the study has a total of 18 questions that are mentioned below:

3.2 Survey based questionnaire

1. The E-government culture can be adopted easily in Pakistan
2. The use of ICT infrastructure is available in Pakistan.
3. There is a perseverance ease of use of ICT to support e-government culture in Pakistan.
4. There is a perseverance of Usefulness of ICT in Pakistan.
5. There is an actual use of e-government system by citizens in Pakistan.
6. The major population are involved in Computer self efficacy in Pakistan.
7. There is a continuous usage of e-government applications in Pakistan
8. The level of willingness in the users of ICT in Pakistan is high.
9. The level of e-government services in Pakistan is quite good.
10. Government of Pakistan has enough financial resources to adopt the culture of e-government in Pakistan.
11. The citizens of Pakistan are supporting to bring the e-government culture.
12. The e-government culture may bring advancements in the field of ICT in Pakistan.
13. The policies of government are in the favor of e-government culture in Pakistan.

14. The deployment of e-government culture in Pakistan may bring positive changes in field of ICT.
15. The expectancy of performance of e-government culture may bring positive changes in field of ICT.
16. The expectancy of efforts of e-government culture may bring positive changes in field of ICT.
17. The social values are influenced by taking e-government culture in Pakistan.
18. The facilitating conditions related to issues and problems in bringing e-government may bring positive changes in Pakistan.

The dependent and independent variable of the research study are based on the survey questionnaire with the perspective of supply and demand which is answered by the 50 participants with the different age groups as described in Table 2. The answer for each question is concerned to the likert scale as shown below.

Table 1: Likert Scale for Survey Questionnaire

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Agree		Strongly Disagree				

From Table 1, it can be seen that if an individual marks on “1” it means the answer for the particular question is strongly agree and if he marks on “5” it reflects strongly disagree.

Table 2: Age of Participation

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 16- 21 years	10	20.0	20.0	20.0
22- 25 years	10	20.0	20.0	40.0
26- 35 years	11	22.0	22.0	62.0
36- 49 years	8	16.0	16.0	78.0
50- 59 years	11	22.0	22.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

4 Analysis and Discussions

4.1 Reliability and validity

The issues related to the reliability and validity must be considered in order to relate the expected data and employed methods directly for conducting a particular research. A set of the methods, a group of steps therefore, is used to improve the reliability of the data and hence, to maximize the validity related to the research. This is important that the level of the reliability and validity in conducting a research must be high which can provide the more meaning of trustworthiness to a particular research. However, the argument is about valuing the validity over the reliability as “a highly reliable test is of little use if it is not valid”. The research study must justify the value of validity as in case, the test is assumed to be not valid, then a highly reliable test is of a little use. The qualitative data is then used which qualifies the approaches belongs to the paradigm. Hence, the paradigm may enhance the potential related to the trustworthiness of the data as well as rigidity of the research as the different sources of the data are used (Cohen, 2000). The research is concern to the adoption

of the e-government system in order to enhance the practical approaches and perseverance use of ease in governmental level.

From Table 3, it can be noted the Cronbach's Alpha is found to be 0.709 which is a good measure to confirm the reliability and validity of the collected data. The researcher by this value can conclude that a high level of internal consistency is present in the collected data gathered from the survey for our scale for a specified sample. The answers provided by the sample are consistent and this consistency provides the enough evidence for reliability and validity of the data.

Table 3: Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Nof Items
.709	18

4.2 Factor Analysis

In continuation to the data is reliable to conduct the further analysis, the use of factor analysis is performed to see whether the correlations are found between the different factors associated with the data and in addition to the loadings. This analysis is performed using the oblique rotation because there is a requirement of the factor loadings which are based on the assumptions of the factors to be correlated. It also provides the evidence to the data for the better suitability to conduct the factor analysis. From Table 4, prior to the factor analysis, the KMO (Kaiser Meyer Olkin) and Bartlett's test significant values are derived.

The sampling adequacy in the KMO is 0.717 which is approximately an evidence for the better sampling; hence, the data is suitable for the study. The result for Chi-square with 66 degrees of freedom is 59.819 with the p-value of 0.060 which is slightly greater than the level of significance 0.05. It can be assumed that the null hypothesis is rejected and the researcher can conclude positive results on the basis of this assumption. In other words, the spearman's rho coefficients may provide the significant correlations amongst the selected variables of both supply and demand side according to the significance level of Bartlett's test.

Table 4: KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser- Meyer- Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.717
Approx. Chi- Square		59.819
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Df	66
	Sig.	.060

In continuation to the KMO and Bartlett's test, Table 5 reflects the item statistics of the selected variables of both demand and supply side. On the left column of Table 5, the description of particular variables is shown. The respected measures of mean (average), standard deviation (variation in the data) and the total number of observations are shown on right side of Table 5. Since, it has already been proved from the reliability and validity of the data that the data shows the reliable measures therefore the standard deviations in the item statistics are not greater than approximately 1.5 which shows that the variation in the data is low. On the contrary, mean shows the average of the variables in the data. From table 1, there were only 5 likert scales in the data therefore the average of the variables lies between 1 and 5.

Table 5: Item Statistics

Items	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
ICT infrastructure availability in Pakistan	2.8600	1.32496	50
Perceived Ease of Use of ICT	3.0000	1.44279	50
Perceived Usefulness of ICT in Pakistan	2.9600	1.41364	50
Actual usage of e- government applications	3.5200	1.37381	50
Computer self efficacy	3.0200	1.46371	50
Continuous usage of e- government applications	2.9200	1.49612	50
Level of Users Willingness	3.0200	1.51846	50
Level of e- government services	2.7000	1.55511	50
Financial Resources	3.3000	1.47427	50
E- government Adoption	3.1600	1.36067	50
Citizen Support to e- government	3.2400	1.55917	50
E- government advancement	3.2400	1.42227	50
Government Policies	2.9800	1.54510	50
E- government deployment	2.9600	1.36964	50
Performance expectancy	3.2400	1.49229	50
Effort expectancy	2.9000	1.50170	50
Social influence	2.6200	1.49680	50
Facilitating condition	3.2000	1.27775	50

4.3 Test of Normality

Many statistical tests required the assumptions to be completed for the test of normality. The data for this test is a prerequisite because in the parametric testing, the data is underlying the assumption. There are two particular methods which are used in SPSS for the purpose of testing normality of the data. Researcher can use numeric as well as graphic method to test the normality of the data. In this particular study, both methods are used.

Table 6 shows the Kolmogorov Smirnov and Shapiro Wilk p-values in the column of significance. The use of Shapiro Wilk test is better for the sample sizes of less than 50. Since, the sample size is exactly 50 in the current research study, therefore in concluding the hypothesis of normality by Shapiro Wilk test is of course no problem. Fortunately, the variables used in the study are related to the qualitative data of both demand and supply side and because of this the p-values are found to be less than 0.05 which portrays the data is normally distributed.

Table 6: Tests of Normality

Items	Kolmogorov- Smirnov ^a			Shapiro- Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
ICT infrastructure availability in Pakistan	.182	50	.000	.903	50	.001
Perceived Ease of Use of ICT	.156	50	.004	.885	50	.000
Perceived Usefulness of ICT in Pakistan	.171	50	.001	.890	50	.000
Actual usage of e-government applications	.199	50	.000	.864	50	.000
Computer self efficacy	.228	50	.000	.866	50	.000
Continuous usage of e-government applications	.231	50	.000	.857	50	.000
Level of Users Willingness	.169	50	.001	.865	50	.000
Level of e-government services	.203	50	.000	.841	50	.000
Financial Resources	.243	50	.000	.853	50	.000
E-government Adoption	.171	50	.001	.897	50	.000
Citizen Support to e-government	.191	50	.000	.845	50	.000
E-government advancement	.243	50	.000	.867	50	.000
Government Policies	.164	50	.002	.857	50	.000
E-government deployment	.156	50	.004	.899	50	.000
Performance expectancy	.181	50	.000	.861	50	.000
Effort expectancy	.157	50	.003	.869	50	.000
Social influence	.201	50	.000	.849	50	.000
Facilitating condition	.166	50	.001	.897	50	.000

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

The graphical method to test the normality of the data is shown in figure 4 with the help of histogram and from figure 5 with the help of NPP (Normal Probability Plot). Figure 4 is showing the symmetric curve in the histogram of dependent variable which is E-government Adoption with respect to the other variables both demand and supply side. The symmetric curve is the evidence for the normality of the data. It can also be noted that the dotted points lies near to the line in the NPP plot in figure 5, which shows the data is normally distributed. Thus, according to the test of normality, the data used in this particular study is normally distributed which supports in meeting the assumptions of statistical tests for the hypothesis of current research study.

4.4 Hypothesis Testing

In order to test the hypothesis of current research study, different statistical analysis will be used such as correlation test, ANOVA and regression analysis (Bwalya, 2012). Since, the data is found to be reliable and valid and also is normally distributed therefore, conducting such tests may provide the trustworthy results for this research study. There are total of 8 hypothesis concerned with this study as already discussed in the previous sections therefore to test those hypothesis, it is really important to conduct the aforementioned tests.

4.5 Correlation Test

The correlation test is an appropriate test to conduct such statistical analysis which derives the relationship between two or more variables. In this study, the researcher is analyzing the linear relationships between the selected variables (Preziosi, 2011). The correlation analysis defined by table 7, demonstrates that about all the variables that are tested through correlation analysis are positively related with E-government adoption except two variables i.e. actual usage of e-government applications and computer self efficacy (Cohen, 2013). These are found negative because of some factors. Firstly, the extent of the use of e-government applications in Pakistan is not very much therefore according to the questionnaire that has been surveyed; the sample described the negative perspectives in adopting the e-government system in Pakistan. Secondly, the computer literacy rate of Pakistan is not much high, also the employees on the governmental level are not much computer literate (Kessides, 2013). The computer literacy rate is low with the measure of 55%. Therefore, this could create one of the major problems for the individuals to adopt the e-government culture when the computer literacy rate is low.

In the adoption of e-government system, consider the situation of citizens' support in bringing an e-government culture to Pakistan. The correlation coefficient between both perspectives is reflecting a good measure i.e. 0.82 which illustrates that the relationship of the e-government adoption with respect to the support of citizen to bring this culture is 82% strong. This relationship occurred because of two factors. The people are keen to bring this culture and they also are not much literate to operate the systems related to e-government. The correlation analysis is helpful in current research study to test H_1 . The correlation coefficient of ICT infrastructure availability in Pakistan, perceived ease of use of ICT and perceived usefulness of ICT in Pakistan to the e-government adoption in Pakistan are found positive i.e. 0.137, 0.218 and 0.152 respectively which provide the enough evidence to illustrate that there is a linear relationship between e-government culture and advancements in ICT in Pakistan.

In order to test the H_2 and H_3 , another table of correlation coefficient is made. In table 8, considering the variables for H_2 , social influence, effort expectancy and performance expectancy that have the positive correlation with the e-government adoption with the correlation coefficients 0.051, 0.152, 0.061 respectively. Thus, the researcher can conclude that there is a linear relationship of social values, efforts expectancy and performance expectancy with e-government culture in Pakistan. Such correlation is a reason for bringing the e-government culture and highlights the expectation of chief efforts and a better performance from the people of Pakistan.

H_3 (3rd hypothesis) is concerned about the e-government deployment and its relation to the government policies of Pakistan. The correlation between the e-government policies and e-government deployment is negative i.e. -0.145. The negative value occurred as according to the perspectives of Pakistanis, the governmental policies do not seem to be in the favor of e-government culture in Pakistan. Thus, the researcher can conclude that the e-government deployment and policies of government are inversely related to each other.

4.6 ANOVA Analysis

The statistical analysis such as ANOVA is used in the current research study, to test the remaining hypotheses such as H_4 , H_5 , H_6 , H_7 and H_8 . The assumptions of test regarding the normality of data and reliability and validity of the data have already been discussed. Therefore there is only the need of considering the value of R-square prior to conduct the test of ANOVA as shown in table 9. Since, R square, also called coefficient of determination denotes the contribution of variance which is 0.58 which illustrates 58% of the variation is explained in the dependent variable by the independent variables.

Table 7: Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.761 ^a	.58	.031	1.38165

a. Predictors: (Constant), Perceived Ease of Use of ICT, Perceived Usefulness of ICT in Pakistan, Government Policies, E- government advancement, Facilitating condition, Citizen Support to e- government, E- government deployment, Computer self efficacy, ICT infrastructure availability in Pakistan, Level of Users Willingness

b. Dependent Variable: E- government Adoption

From table 10, the F-stat is 2.45 and p-value is 0.02 which is less than the level of significance 0.05. The p-value concludes that the all the null hypothesis relating to the e-government adoption as dependent variable and other variables as independent, is rejected. Since, in conducting the ANOVA test the researcher uses all the variables and apply ANOVA therefore the results are shown for the overall hypothesis which does not provide the clear picture of the research hypothesis. The use of the regression analysis will provide the appropriate results for the hypotheses separately which will be supportive in fulfilling the requirements of the research study (Bonsón, 2012).

Table 8: ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	18.179	11	1.653	2.4507	.020 ^b
Residual	72.541	38	1.909		
Total	90.720	49			

a. Dependent Variable: E- government Adoption

b. Predictors: (Constant), Perceived Ease of Use of ICT, Perceived Usefulness of ICT in Pakistan, Government Policies, E- government advancement, Facilitating condition, Citizen Support to e- government, E- government deployment, Computer self efficacy, ICT infrastructure availability in Pakistan, Level of Users Willingness

4.6 Regression Analysis

The use of regression analysis is performed to answer each hypothesis separately. The ANOVA test, in table 10 provided the results of overall hypothesis which did not clarify the e-government adoption in Pakistan with supply and demand perspectives. The predictive or regression equation with the help of table 11 can be constructed. In table 11, the coefficients and intercept of the regression equation are shown which helps the researcher to identify the positive or negative relation of the independent variables to the dependent variables separately.

Regression Equation

$$E_GOV_Adopt = \text{intercept (constant)} + ICT_Infra * 0.105 - Comp_SE * 0.136 + Users_Will * 0.251 + Citizen_Supp * 0.008 - E_GOV_ADV * 0.045 - GOV_POL * 0.012 + PER_EASE_USE * 0.55 - E_GOV_DEP * 0.364 + PER_USEFUL * 0.029 + FAC_CONDI * 0.268 + e_i$$

H₄ is concerned about the perceived ease of use of websites which relates to e-government influence on e-government culture in Pakistan. From table 11, there is a positive coefficient of the perseverance ease of use of websites and the e-government adoption in Pakistan therefore it can be said that there is a direct relation in the two variables. Hence, the p-value may identify that null hypothesis is false and researcher can conclude that more the people are perceived of the web and applications, more the e-government system may be adopted in Pakistan.

On the other hand, H₅ is also concerned about the perceived usefulness of websites related to e-government will positively supported by citizens of Pakistan to bring e-government culture. From table 11, the coefficients of both perceived usefulness of application and citizen support are positive, therefore there is also the direct relationship between e-government adoption to the complete use of e-government websites and citizen's support to bring the e-government system in Pakistan. The p-value illustrates that the null hypothesis is false which elaborates alternative hypothesis to be true.

H₆ is concerned about the proper use of ICT infrastructure may impact positively on e-government culture in perseverance ease of use. The coefficient of ICT infrastructure and people perceiving the ease of the websites are positive to the e-government adoption which also leads to reject the null hypothesis therefore the researcher may conclude that the proper use of ICT infrastructure may impact positively on e-government system in perseverance ease of use.

H₇ concerns the level of user's willingness in ICT may directly influence the intentions to engage e-government culture in Pakistan. From table 11, again the coefficients and p-value of user willingness and ICT infra structure may lead to reject the null hypothesis. The researcher with respect to the measures in table 11 can conclude that the level of user's willingness in ICT may directly influence the intentions to engage e-government culture in Pakistan.

H₈ also concerns about the attributes of level of computer self-efficacy which could impact on the actual use of an e-government system in Pakistan. The p-value is less than level of significance 0.05 for computer self efficacy and the coefficient in table 11 is also negative which tends to accept the null hypothesis. Hence, the researcher may conclude that there is a negative or low level of computer self efficacy among the people of Pakistan that directly impacts on the use of e-government system and its adoption in Pakistan.

5 Limitations of the Study

In this study, the first limitation is that a purposeful sampling strategy was used from one city in the Pakistan. The perceptions of these citizens may differ from those in other cities or states. Although many of the barriers that citizens face who use public services in one city may be experienced in other cities, no generalization is being attempted. Second, it was impossible to interview the entire population of citizens who use public services in Pakistan due to time and resources constraints. It is also important to note that although study participants currently live in Pakistan some may have relocated from other states or surrounding areas. A sample of the citizens was obtained from users of the Public services in Pakistan. Another limitation of the study was financial resources. Time restriction can also limit the findings of the study.

6 Conclusion

In conclusion, with the help of above analysis and discussions the adoption of e-government system remains a big issue in Pakistan until the problems and obstacles related to it are not solved. The main cause for the bad adoption of e-government culture is the shortage of electricity. The load shedding should be stopped in order to implement such system otherwise it seems impossible. Secondly, the issues of ICT infrastructure should be taken into account to adopt such system for the betterment of the country. The policies of the government must be in the favor of the e-government deployment to provide the perseverance use of ICT in Pakistan which will bring a positive change in e-government system. The UTAUT model can be essential for the government of Pakistan to understand how to incorporate the demand side factors in e-government adoption (Im, 2011).

There is a need for the government and also for the people of the country that they should take actions with the perspectives of both, supply and demand to incorporate the e-government culture. The performance and efforts of the people of Pakistan with are demanded with relation to the computer self efficacy to become more stabilized country in the world. The government of Pakistan, management of the firms, leaders and scholars, must take the positive actions in improving the policies and strategies and in providing the enough financial resources in favor of e-government adoption (Ahmad, 2013). Concerning to the literacy rate, positive and serious actions are to be taken by the government as well as by the citizens in the field of education to make the aim of the e-government culture possible. The government of Pakistan should look into the causes to provide a solution for aforementioned problems in order to adopt the e-government culture.

References

- Ahmad, M. O., Markkula, J., & Oivo, M. (2012), Factors influencing the adoption of e-government services in Pakistan. In *Proceedings of the 9th European, Mediterranean & Middle Eastern Conference on Information Systems*. Retrieved from http://www.researchgate.net/profile/Muhammad_Ovais_Ahmad/publication/260344620_FACTORS_IN_FLUENCING_THE_ADOPTION_OF_E-GOVERNMENT_SERVICES_IN_PAKISTAN/links/546b4a860cf2397f7831ba16.pdf
- Alomari, M., Woods, P., & Sandhu, K. (2012), Predictors for e-government adoption in Jordan: Deployment of an empirical evaluation based on a citizen-centric approach. *Information Technology & People*, 25(2), 207-234. Retrieved from <http://www.seu.ac.lk/fmc/mit/freedownload/Predictors%20for%20e-government%20adoption%20in%20Jordan%20Deployment%20of%20an%20empirical%20evaluation%20based%20on%20a%20citizen-centric%20approach.pdf>
- Alshehri, M. A. (2012), Using the UTAUT Model to Determine Factors Affecting Acceptance and Use of E-government Services in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. Retrieved from https://www120.secure.griffith.edu.au/rch/file/1c7cab3e-da14-452a-8379-95387756bd56/1/Alshehri_2013_02Thesis.pdf
- Bhutto, A. W., Bazmi, A. A., & Zahedi, G. (2013), Greener energy: Issues and challenges for Pakistan—wind power prospective. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 20, 519-538. Retrieved from http://www.academia.edu/download/30904011/Greener_energy-Issues_and_challenges_for_Pakistan-wind_power_prospective.pdf
- Bohari, A. M., & Zainuddin, N. (2013), Computerization of Seaport Operation Management: Competitive Issues and Need of ICT Advancement. *Information Management & Business Review*, 5(5). Retrieved from <http://www.ifrnd.org/Research%20Papers/I55.pdf>
- Bonsón, E., Torres, L., Royo, S., & Flores, F. (2012). Local e-government 2.0: Social media and corporate transparency in municipalities. *Government information quarterly*, 29(2), 123-132. Retrieved from http://www.aeca1.org/pub/on_line/comunicaciones_xvicongresoaeaca/cd/18f.pdf
- Bwalya, K. J., Du Plessis, T., & Rensleigh, C. (2012). E-government awareness and development in Zambia: challenges and opportunities for inclusiveness. *Mousaion*, 30(2), 69-91. Retrieved from https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=1&ved=0CBsQFjAA&url=http%3A%2F%2Fwww.ejeg.com%2Fissue%2Fdownload.html%3FidArticle%3D241&ei=jUP7VPz2LYGrUtv8gagH&usg=AFQjCNH0_yx_z9HvAD_zK0dwnGHGI_FSxg&bvm=bv.87611401,d.ZGU&cad=rja
- Cohen, J., Cohen, P., West, S. G., & Aiken, L. S. (2013), *Applied multiple regression/correlation analysis for the behavioral sciences*, Routledge.
- Im, I., Hong, S., & Kang, M. S. (2011). An international comparison of technology adoption: Testing the UTAUT model. *Information & Management*, 48(1), 1-8.
- Jaeger, P. T., & Matteson, M. (2009). e-government and technology acceptance: The case of the implementation of section 508 guidelines for websites. *Electronic Journal of e-Government*, 7(1), 87-98. Retrieved from https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=5&ved=0CDgQFjAE&url=http%3A%2F%2Fwww.ejeg.com%2Fissue%2Fdownload.html%3FidArticle%3D182&ei=1EP7VKTpMsvzUNi8guAO&usg=AFQjCNExUJbFtj7qQtbmFL9_aYQXopQ-uw&bvm=bv.87611401,d.ZGU&cad=rja
- Kaul, V. (2014), An Exploration of the Potentials and Potencies of Information & Communication technologies for Educational Development. Retrieved from http://ajocict.net/uploads/V7N5P6-2014_AJOCICT.pdf
- Kessides, I. N. (2013), Chaos in power: Pakistan's electricity crisis. *Energy policy*, 55, 271-285.
- Krishnan, S., & Teo, T. S. (2012), Moderating effects of governance on information infrastructure and e-government development. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 63(10), 1929-1946.

- Mahmood, M., Osmani, M., & Sivarajah, U. (2014), The Role of Trust in E-Government Adoption: A Systematic Literature Review.
- Manzoor, A. (2013), The Dynamics of Broadband Internet Market in Pakistan. *International Journal of Information*, 2(2). Retrieved from <http://warse.org/pdfs/2013/ijiscs01222013.pdf>
- Ovais Ahmad, M., Markkula, J., & Oivo, M. (2013). Factors affecting e-government adoption in Pakistan: a citizen's perspective. *Transforming Government: People, Process and Policy*, 7(2), 225-239. Retrieved from <http://www.seu.ac.lk/cedpl/freedownload/00%20Paper%20Factors%20affecting%20e-government%20adoption%20in%20Pakistan.pdf>
- Preziosi, R., McLaughlin, H. M., & McLaughlin, G. C. (2011), The Relationship Of Learning Orientation To Organizational Performance, *Journal of Business & Economics Research (JBER)*, 2(4).
- Rahman, T. (2014), The Internet, Youth and Education in Pakistan. Retrieved from <http://nhdr.undp.org/wp-content/uploads/2015/02/Taimur-Rahman-Internet-Youth-Education-in-Pakistan.pdf>
- Rehman, M., Esichaikul, V., & Kamal, M. (2012), Factors influencing e-government adoption in Pakistan. *Transforming Government: People, Process and Policy*, 6(3), 258-282.
- Snead, J. T., & Wright, E. (2014), E-government research in the United States. *Government Information Quarterly*, 31(1), 129-136.
- Wicander, G. (2011), Mobile Supported e-Government Systems: Analysis of the Education Management Information System (EMIS) in Tanzania. Retrieved from <http://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:447593/FULLTEXT01.pdf>